

Allicin as a Potential Inducer of Apoptosis in Cancer Cells

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Abstract

Allicin is a biologically active component, present in freshly sliced garlic cloves (*Allium sativum*). It has been used by Indians, Greeks, Egyptians and Chinese to treat various diseases such as cardio-vascular complications, arthritis, pulmonary congestions, abdominal over-growth, diarrhea and worm infestations.

Garlic extracts have been found to restrict active propagation of cells during the episodes of skin, breast, uterine, cervix and colon cancer. It has anti-bacterial, anti-viral & anti-parasitic effects and is known to reduce platelet aggregation and induce apoptosis in tumor cells of different tissue origin due to the presence of many organo-sulphur compounds. It is presumed that apoptosis brings about cell-shrinkage, chromatin condensation and stimulation of specific cysteine proteases known as caspases. Studies are underway to understand the mechanism that induces anti-proliferation and apoptosis in tumor cells.

Key Words: Allicin, Anti-proliferation, Apoptosis, Cancer, Tumor.

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